

Factors Influencing Online Impulse Buying Behavior: Evidence from Shopee Live

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ABSTRACT

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This study aims to investigate the factors that influence online impulse buying behavior among Indonesian consumers on the Shopee Live e-commerce platform. With the advent of digital technology, shopping behavior has shifted significantly towards online platforms, particularly through innovative features such as live streaming. Utilizing a purposive sampling technique, data was collected from Shopee users through a Google Forms and analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). The research findings revealed that factors such as time pressure, quantity pressure, and social influence did not significantly influence enjoyment leading to the absence of impulse buying online. Whereas the results of economic benefits, visual elements and sound elements on enjoyment were highly significant which played an important role in driving impulse purchase decisions. This suggests that consumers are more attracted to tangible economic benefits such as discounts and attractive visual and sound ornament presentations during live streaming sessions. The study concludes that enhancing these key visual and economic factors can effectively increase impulse buying behavior, offering valuable insights for retailers and marketers looking to optimize their strategies in a live commerce environment.

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1. Introduction

The way Indonesians shop has changed significantly as a result of the rise of digital technology. One of innovation in the realm of e-commerce is live streaming. This strategy, which initially took off in China, has seen remarkable success and has since spread to countries like the United States, Indonesia, and beyond (Roostika et al., 2024). Online shopping is more popular than traditional retail shopping (Afif & Purwanto, 2020). One of the most common types of changes is e-commerce, which allows customers to make purchases online quickly and easily (Silitonga et al., 2024). Shopee is one of the most well-known e-commerce sites and is widely used by the Indonesian people. (Fatimah & Adinugraha, 2024). Shopee continues to innovate by presenting a variety of features designed to improve the shopping experience of customers. One of the features introduced is the live streaming feature (Silitonga et al., 2024). This is because live streaming is used to increase sales

through interactive connections between customers and streamers on a platform (Kinasih & Wuryandari, 2023). Several aspects of live shopping, such as real-time interactions with sellers, time-limited discounts, and attractive product displays, can encourage consumers to make purchases without much consideration (L. Li & Kang, 2023). According to Nuryani et al., (2022), promotion is one of the factors that affect a person's impulse purchases. Research by Daroch et al., (2021) and Gasimov et al., (2024) highlights that the convenience of online shopping greatly increases impulse buying tendencies. An easy shopping experience on a platform like Shopee, which provides user-friendly navigation and display, can facilitate more impulsive shopping behavior. Sales promotion is a carefully planned and strategic combination that directly persuades consumers to buy a good or service. The purpose of this study is to test the variables that affect the impulsive purchase decisions of Indonesian consumers on e-commerce platforms, especially on the Shopee Live shopping feature.

The importance of understanding impulse buying behavior in the digital age, especially in developing countries such as Indonesia. With the increasing use of e-commerce platforms, knowledge of the factors that influence consumer behavior can help marketers in designing more effective promotional strategies (Almasyhari et al., 2024). This research also contributes to the literature on consumer behavior and digital marketing in Indonesia, while providing practical insights for businesses in the e-commerce sector. Some previous studies have shown that hedonic factors, such as satisfaction and entertainment, have a major influence on impulse purchase decisions (Ngo et al., 2024). However, these limitations often do not consider the specific context of the e-commerce platform used, such as Shopee Live, so the results cannot be generalized.

2. Theoretical Framework

Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)

According to Li & Kang (2023). The TPB offers a useful theoretical framework for investigating how attitudes, perceived behavioral controls, and subjective norms affect purchase intent. The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) explains that an individual's intention to perform a specific action is the strongest predictor of whether they will actually engage in that behavior. This intention is influenced by three key factors: the person's attitude towards the behavior, the subjective norms surrounding it, and their perceived control over the behavior (Wei et al., 2025). In the context of impulse buying, the act of buying spontaneously after consumers enter a store's live streaming feature can be categorized as an impulse purchase (Amalia & Firmialy, 2024). Unique features such as real-time video interaction and online payment system services offer a distinctive appeal to consumers. This, as explained by Li & Kang, (2023) can trigger impulse buying behavior among online consumers. Therefore, it is imperative to use the TPB in the current study in exploring consumers' impulse purchase intentions and behaviors on online platforms.

Shopee Live

Shopee is one of the most famous e-commerce sites and is widely used by Indonesians (Fatimah & Adinugraha, 2024). Shopee continues to innovate by presenting various features designed to improve customers' shopping experience. One of the features introduced is the live streaming feature (Silitonga et al., 2024). Live streaming commerce is an emerging business model and much of its potential has yet to be fully explored (Xu et al., 2020). In live streaming, sellers or hosts broadcast live to offer products, demonstrate how to use them, and answer questions or comments from the audience in real-time. Shopee is a platform that is widely used by online shopping users in Indonesia, reaching 83.4%. To increase sales through interactive connections between customers and streamers on a platform, retailers and influencers use live streaming as a marketing tool (Kinasih & Wuryandari, 2023).

Time Pressure

Time Pressure refers to the limited time given to make a purchase decision quickly, which can provide a strong incentive for consumers to enjoy and feel happy while shopping (Ngo et al., 2024). Time pressure has been shown to trigger satisfaction so that it can increase the willingness of decision-makers to take risks (Adam et al., 2015). Flash sale offers or discounts with a certain time limit on Shopee's live streaming feature create high time pressure. Consumers feel that they must act immediately to get the exclusive offer (Ngo et al., 2024). Without the time pressure of live streaming, consumers tend to spend more time reviewing more relevant product information before making a purchase decision (Liu et al., 2017). **H1:** Time Pressure has a significant impact on Pleasure.

Quantity Pressure

Quantity Pressure is a strategy of scarcity quantity is its ability to increase the perceived value of the goods offered. By limiting the number of products, seller create the perception that the products has a high transaction value, thereby increasing its attractiveness to consumers (Qu, Khan, et al., 2023). Quantity pressure can affect pleasure in impulse purchases, especially through the live shopping feature (Ngo et al., 2024). Quantity restrictions create a perception of scarcity, which increases consumer urgency and thus encourages impulse buying decisions. **H2:** Quantity Pressure has a significant impact on Pleasure.

Economic Benefit

Research by Rook & Fisher (1995) shows that discounts and promotions can create a sense of urgency, encouraging consumers to make impulse buying decisions. Economic Benefit in the form of pricing strategy during live streaming can significantly encourage consumers to make impulse purchases. According to the research of Chen and Yao (2018) in Ngo et al., (2024), savings obtained through discounts or other economic incentives can generate a strong positive boost for consumers.

Economic benefits can create a significant impact on consumer satisfaction, making it a strategic element in live shopping marketing activities on the Shopee platform. **H3:** Economic Benefit has a significant impact on Pleasure.

Social Influence

Social influence is one of the main causes of impulse buying, especially when shopping while live streaming (Ngo et al., 2024). Interaction, when the host carries the streaming, will create a closer and more real-feeling experience for the customer, even though it happens in an online environment (G. Li et al., 2022). Accurate and precise information also can help buyers make informed decisions and increase their confidence in purchasing (Faizza & Roostika, 2024). Social influence has a positive effect on the level of consumer satisfaction in shopping online through the live streaming feature. Support from peers or influencers, as well as interaction within online communities, can increase consumer enthusiasm and engagement during the shopping process (Ngo et al., 2024; Simamora et al., 2024). Qu, Cieslik, et al., (2023) and Seber (2018) examined the importance of social interaction in the context of online purchasing, noting that engagement with sellers or streamers can increase the level of trust that drives impulse purchases. **H4:** Social Influence has a significant impact on Pleasure.

Visual

Visual marketing is a strategic way to convey product information to consumers with the aim of increasing sales. This strategy aims to arouse consumer interest through visual appeal that is able to create a deep impression and attract their attention to intend to buy (Chiu, 2022; Guo et al., 2021). Attractive visual elements spark emotional arousal, which in turn increases the positive perception of the shopping experience and consumer satisfaction (Ngo et al., 2024; Verhagen & van Dolen, 2011). In addition, well-designed visuals help consumers understand the product more easily, thereby increasing satisfaction with the purchase decision (Guo et al., 2021). **H5:** Visual has a significant impact on Pleasure.

Sound

Background music can affect a person's emotional reactions, which can ultimately encourage impulsive buying behavior. This is because the interactive sound background encourages consumers to actively participate, both through comments and by following the flow of the event (Ngo et al., 2024). Sound elements, such as background music and dynamic sound effects, have a positive influence on consumer passion. Sound elements influence consumer satisfaction by creating a more enjoyable and interactive shopping atmosphere. Sound that triggers emotional arousal increases the positive perception of the shopping experience, which ultimately increases consumer satisfaction (Ngo et al., 2024; Verhagen & van Dolen, 2011). **H6:** Sound has a significant impact on Pleasure.

Pleasure

The pleasure felt can create a pleasant shopping experience, which then encourages individuals to make purchases without careful planning (Verhagen & van Dolen, 2011). Satisfaction plays an important role in triggering impulse purchases online. When consumers feel satisfaction and happiness during a live streaming session, they are more likely to make impulse purchases. This is due to the fact that positive emotions such as happiness can reduce rational judgment in the purchase decision process (Ngo et al., 2024). **H7:** Pleasure has a significant impact on Online Impulse Buying.

Online Impulse Buying

Impulse Buying is the process of purchasing goods or products that are carried out without prior planning. This behavior usually arises when consumers suddenly feel a strong urge to buy an item immediately (Pranggabayu & Lestari Andjarwati, 2022). In the Asian, impulsive buying behavior is significantly influenced by an emphasis on individualistic aspects, such as personal needs, desires, and hedonic pleasures. This focus often leads to a heightened tendency for impulsive purchases (Pujiastuti et al., 2022). Impulse purchases in live commerce have become a significant source of revenue. For example, during the 2020 Shopping Festival, live commerce sales reached \$6 billion globally, reflecting a huge opportunity for companies to invest in this industry (Makmor et al., 2024).

3. Method

This study uses a quantitative methodology. Structural equation modeling, or SEM, was used in this study. The population in this study is Shopee users. Sampling in this study uses a non-probability sampling technique. The data collection technique was carried out using the distribution of questionnaires. The survey uses a Google Forms questionnaire that is distributed online using the researcher's personal social media accounts, Whatsapp and Instagram.

Descriptive analysis was used in this study to describe the profiles or characteristics of the respondents the result was 62,6% women and 37,4% men. Respondents in this study mostly were between 20 and 25 years old. The average monthly expenses for most of the respondents is less than Rp. 2.000.000, namely 47,1%. The average time spent on Shopee in a day is more than 3 hours per day amounting to 26,4% of 227 respondents.

This research uses the Likert Scale as a means of measuring respondents' agreement or disagreement with questionnaire items, used to assess responses. The scale is named after Rensis Likert, who published a report explaining its use. People or a collection of people's attitudes, views and perceptions towards a symptom or phenomenon can be evaluated using a Likert scale (Nugroho & Mawardi, 2021). This questionnaire includes items designed to evaluate various factors that potentially influence impulse buying behavior, such as time pressure, quantity

pressure, economic benefits, social influence, visuals, sounds, pleasure, and online impulsive buying. Respondents were asked to rate their level of agreement with each item on a scale that ranged from seven types of Likert scales used are:

1. Strongly disagree
2. Disagree
3. Slightly disagree
4. Neutral
5. Slightly agree
6. Agree
7. Strongly agree

This study utilized various techniques, such as convergent validity, reliability, and discriminant validity. Convergent validity is tested by ensuring that all items in the questionnaire measure the same construct, which is calculated through Outer Loadings and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values, with values over 0.50 indicating good validity. Reliability testing is done using Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability, where values above 0.60 indicate good consistency of the research instrument (Haji-Othman & Yusuff, 2022). Discriminant validity is used to ensure that each measured construct is significantly different from other constructs, which is tested by comparing the variance estimates of each construct. In Fig. 1, Through the use of appropriate instruments and validity techniques, this research seeks to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the data collected, so that the results of the study can provide valid and relevant insights into impulse buying behavior on Shopee Live.

Fig. 1. Theoretical Framework
Source: Thuy et al., 2024

4. Result and Discussion

Convergent validity and reliability of constructs

The purpose of validity testing is to assess the accuracy of the instrument before it is used in a study (Al Hakim et al, 2021). Based on the results in Fig. 2, of Outer Loadings are more than more than 0.50. Shows that outer loading has results, namely (EB1 0,724; EB2 0,818; EB3 0,745; EB4 0,763; EB5 0,749) (OIB1 0,893; OIB2 0,909; OIB3 0,905; OIB4 0,826) (P1 0,917; P2 0,949; P3 0,908; P4 0,855) (QP1 0,824; QP2 0,851; QP3 0,909; QP4 0,888) (S1 0,941; S2 0,945; S3 0,930; S4 0,918) (SI2 0,763; SI3 0,878; SI4 0,814) (TP1 0,737; TP2 0,818; TP3 0,750; TP4 0,757) (V1 0,869; V2 0,881; V3 0,914; V4 0,877).

Fig. 2. Outer Measurement Model

Source: Data Processing, 2024

Table 1. Validity and reliability

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	AVE
EB.1	0.819	0.873	0.578
OIB.1	0.906	0.934	0.781
PL.1	0.928	0.949	0.824
QP.1	0.891	0.925	0.755
SO.1	0.951	0.964	0.871
SI.2	0.758	0.860	0.672
TP.1	0.765	0.850	0.587
VS.1	0.909	0.936	0.784

SOURCE: DATA PROCESSING, 2024

Average Variance Extracted (AVE) in Table 1 above, it can be declared valid because it is above the criteria, which is more than 0.50. and Based on Table 1, Cronbach alpha (α) and Composite Reliability, which more than 0.60, the research data is considered very good and reliable to be used as input in the data analysis process.

Discriminant validity of construct

Discriminant validity refers to the extent to which a construct is truly different from other constructs based on empirical standards. One method to determine the discriminant validity of a construct is through the application of the Fornell-Larcker Criterion and Heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT) (Jr, 2014). Based on Table 2, since the square root of the AVE (diagonal value) of each construct should be higher than its correlation with other components (off-diagonal value), it can be seen that all variables are discriminantly valid.

Table 2. Fornell Larcker Criterion

	EB	OIB	PL	QP	SI	SO	TP	VS
EB	0.761							
OIB	0.482	0.884						
PL	0.592	0.545	0.908					
QP	0.588	0.577	0.570	0.869				
SI	0.469	0.510	0.541	0.504	0.820			
SO	0.462	0.593	0.644	0.508	0.602	0.934		
TP	0.498	0.587	0.437	0.583	0.479	0.486	0.766	
VS	0.521	0.461	0.661	0.481	0.514	0.712	0.378	0.885

SOURCE: DATA PROCESSING, 2024

Notes: Economic Benefit, Online Impulse Buying, Pleasure, Quantity Pressure, Social Influence, Sound, Time Pressure, Visual.

Table 3. Heterotrait-monotrait ration (HTMT)

	EB	OIB	PL	QP	SI	SO	TP	VS
EB								
OIB	0.526							
PL	0.662	0.591						
QP	0.674	0.642	0.627					
SI	0.567	0.591	0.634	0.599				
SO	0.503	0.638	0.683	0.551	0.691			
TP	0.604	0.701	0.515	0.700	0.616	0.570		
VS	0.595	0.501	0.711	0.528	0.608	0.761	0.448	

SOURCE: DATA PROCESSING 2024

As seen Table 3, shows that the HTMT values of all variables have met the requirements, which are below 0.85. This indicates that the test results are approved. Thus, it can be said that each variable in this study is discriminatively valid.

Path Coefficients

Path coefficient is usually between -1 and +1, where a significant positive relationship is indicated by a coefficient close to +1, while a strong negative relationship is indicated by a coefficient close to -1 (Jr et al., 2021; Sarstedt et al., 2021).

Table 4. Path Coefficients result

		Original Sample	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
H1	TP → PL	-0.023	-0.018	0.054	0.424	0.672
H2	QP → PL	0.164	0.152	0.116	1.419	0.157
H3	EB → PL	0.220	0.227	0.057	3.870	0.000
H4	SI → PL	0.094	0.101	0.059	1.584	0.114
H5	VS → PL	0.270	0.262	0.070	3.877	0.000
H6	SO → PL	0.221	0.228	0.089	2.471	0.014
H7	PL → OIB	0.545	0.548	0.059	9.175	0.000

SOURCE: DATA PROCESSING, 2024

Path coefficient can be said to have significance if it is in line with the principle of Junior et al., (2014), stipulating that the P-value must be below 0.05 and the t-stat value must be more than 1.96. Based on the results of Table 4, it can be concluded that H1, H2, H5, H7 are significantly accepted, whereas H3, H4, H6 are rejected and not significant.

Coefficient Determination/R-Square

Based on the R square test results in Fig. 3, below shows that the pleasure variable has a value of 57.4%. this shows that 42.6% there are still variables that are not related to pleasure that still have an impact. thus, the online impulse buying variable of 29.3% describes online impulse buying. This illustrates that other than the online impulse buying variable still has an impact of 70.7%.

Fig. 3. Bootstrapping Structural Model
Source: Data Processing, 2024

Discussion

This study investigates the factors influencing online impulsive buying behavior, particularly among Indonesian consumers on the Shopee live platform. This focused on exploring the impacts of external stimuli including time pressure (TP), quantity pressure (QP), economic benefits (EB), social influence (SI), visual (VS), and sound (SO) on online impulsive buying (OIB), mediated by pleasure (PL). Based on result of this study, factors that influence users' pleasure in live streaming sessions include economic benefits, visual elements, and sound elements, which are shown to be significant in increasing the level of pleasure. In contrast, factors such as time pressure, quantity pressure, and social influence did not show significant influence on pleasure levels and did not drive impulse purchases. This study also found that consumers are more attracted to obvious economic benefits, such as discounts, as well as attractive visual and sound presentations, which directly influence impulse purchase decisions.

Impacts of time pressure on pleasure

This study shows that time pressure does not have a significant effect on pleasure. this means that not all consumers can accept time pressure that can increase their sense of pleasure. because they will feel rushed which will not encourage the role of impulse buying.

Impacts of quantity pressure on pleasure

The results of this study, the quantity pressure variable was rejected. that is, the effect of quantity pressure faced by consumers does not fully make them feel happy which results in no encouragement to make impulse purchases.

Impacts of economic benefit on pleasure

As evidenced by the results of this study, economic benefits have a major impact on pleasure. that is, the higher the price discount offer given, the more it increases the consumer's sense of pleasure to buy impulsively that has not been planned in advance.

Impact of social influence on pleasure

Social influence does not have a significant effect on pleasure in Shopee live streaming shopping because consumer satisfaction is more influenced by direct interaction with streamers and personal experiences during live streaming sessions rather than external influences from the social environment.

Impact of visual on pleasure

Visuals have a significant influence on the pleasure of shopping on Shopee live streams because an attractive visual display can create a more comfortable and enjoyable shopping experience. In the context of live streaming, visual elements such as image quality, product layout, as well as live demonstrations provide real-time product information, which can encourage shopping without prior planning.

Impact of sound on pleasure

Sound has a significant effect on pleasure when shopping on Shopee live streaming because audio elements can enhance the emotional experience and consumer engagement. Engaging sounds, such as upbeat background music and friendly streamer voice intonations, create a more fun and entertaining atmosphere during shopping sessions. Research shows that positive sounds can trigger a deep emotional response, amplifying consumers' sense of pleasure and comfort when interacting with products.

Impact of pleasure on online impulsive buying

Pleasure has a significant effect on online impulse buying in Shopee live streaming shopping because the positive emotions that consumers feel during shopping sessions can reduce rational control and encourage spontaneous purchasing decisions. Research shows that interactive elements such as direct communication with streamers, interesting product demonstrations, and an entertaining shopping atmosphere create an intense sense of pleasure, so consumers are more easily encouraged to buy without prior planning. In addition, these pleasurable experiences are often amplified by exclusive promotions or discounts offered on a limited basis during live streaming sessions, which increases urgency and triggers impulsive behavior.

This study is consistent with previous studies such as [Ngo et al., \(2024\)](#) which showed that hedonic factors such as pleasure and entertainment have a large impact on impulse buying decisions. However, this study contributes more deeply by showing that in the context of Shopee Live, engaging visual and audio factors may function more effectively than social factors in increasing impulsivity. As such, the enhancement of visual elements and economic benefits in e-commerce platforms such as Shopee Live would be a more beneficial strategy versus focusing on social themes or time pressure.

5. Conclusion

The purpose of this study was to determine how impulse buying driven in consumers when live streaming at Shopee is influenced by time pressure, quantity pressure, economic benefits, social impact, visual, sound, pleasure on impulse purchases. The results showed that arousal, pleasure, quantity pressure, social influence, and time pressure had no significant effect on impulse buying online. The results showed that economic benefits, pleasure, sound, and visuals have a significant effect on impulse purchases online. meaning that consumers focus more on direct economic benefits (such as discounts or special offers) and attractive visual and sound experiences. These factors may influence purchasing decisions more profoundly because consumers tend to make impulsive decisions based on elements that are more concrete and visually or emotionally appealing, while fun, quantity pressure, social influence, and time pressure are not strong enough to drive impulsive behavior in those situations. From the results of this study, the researcher

suggests that business actors optimize visual and audio elements in live streaming sessions and offer time-limited attractive promotions to enhance the shopping experience and encourage impulse purchases. Future researchers can explore more deeply the relationship between various external factors and how they interact with consumer behavior in different contexts.

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